

DOPPLEROGRAPHIC STUDY RESULTS OF THE OVARIES AND UTERUS AFTER LIGATION OF THREE PAIRS OF UTERINE VESSELS AND COMPRESSION SUTURING OF THE UTERUS

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Abstract. *Obstetric hemorrhage remains a leading cause of maternal mortality, accounting for up to 27% of cases worldwide. When conservative methods fail to control bleeding, organ-preserving surgical techniques are employed, though their long-term consequences are insufficiently studied in the literature. This study aims to examine the hemodynamics of the uterus and ovaries in 33 patients who experienced obstetric blood loss and underwent organ-preserving procedures. The study revealed a reduction in the mean diameter of the right uterine artery (UA) by 11.9% and the left UA by 16.6%, along with a 1.3-fold decrease in blood flow velocity (Vmax). There was an increase in the pulsatility index (PI) in the right UA by 39.4% and in the left UA by 41.6%, as well as a rise in the resistance index (RI) in the right UA by 29.9% and in the left UA by 36.4%, indicating the presence of high-resistance blood flow. Additionally, the arterial perfusion index (API) was reduced by 33.3% compared to the control group. These findings suggest that decreased blood supply to the uterus and ovaries may lead to anovulatory cycles or insufficient corpus luteum function, potentially resulting in infertility or hypoluteinism, as well as early pregnancy loss.*

Keywords: *obstetric hemorrhage, organ-preserving surgery, Doppler ultrasound of uterine and ovarian arteries, peripheral resistance, arterial perfusion index.*

Introduction. Obstetric hemorrhage remains a leading cause of maternal mortality, accounting for up to 27% of cases worldwide [3, 6, 12]. In recent years, when conservative methods prove ineffective, surgical interventions have been increasingly utilized, primarily focusing on organ-preserving techniques such as uterine devascularization via ligation of three pairs of uterine vessels, compression suturing of the uterus, internal iliac artery ligation, or their combination [3, 5, 6, 12, 13]. While these methods demonstrate high efficacy in preserving the uterus, research on their long-term effects in women who have experienced pathological blood loss during childbirth and undergone organ-preserving surgeries remains insufficient.

Literature Review and Study Objectives

The available literature on the reproductive health of women who have undergone organ-preserving surgical interventions during childbirth is contradictory and largely limited to case series descriptions [7, 8, 9, 10, 11]. The issues of ovarian and uterine perfusion in relation to the specific techniques of organ-preserving surgeries remain insufficiently studied [14].

Given this, the present study aimed to investigate the hemodynamics of the uterus and ovaries in patients with obstetric hemorrhages who underwent organ-preserving surgeries. The following objectives were established to achieve this goal:

- Assess the blood supply to the uterine and ovarian arteries using ultrasound with color Doppler mapping (CDM).
- Calculate the uterine arterial perfusion index (API).

Materials and Methods

The study group included 33 patients who experienced pathological blood loss and underwent compression suturing after unsuccessful ligation of three pairs of uterine vessels. The control group consisted of 25 patients without pathological blood loss or organ-preserving surgeries.

The study was conducted using modern ultrasound machines equipped with transvaginal probes, scanning in CDM mode following standard gynecological pelvic examination protocols [4]. All patients underwent ultrasound assessment of blood flow velocity and peripheral resistance in the uterine and intraovarian circulation, including resistance index (RI), pulsatility index (PI), and systolic-diastolic ratio (SDR).

The volumetric blood flow rate (per 1 cm³ per cardiac cycle) in each uterine artery (UA) was calculated using the following formula:

$V_{vol} = V_{mean} \cdot S$, where **S** is the cross-sectional area of the uterine artery (cm²).

Additionally, the arterial perfusion index (API) was determined, reflecting the perfusion of 1 cm³ of the uterine body by blood supplied through both uterine arteries, expressed as a percentage. The calculations were performed according to the methodology described by I.A. Ozerskaya [4], using the formula:

$ИАП = (V_{vol} MA_{right} + V_{vol} MA_{left}) / V_{uterus}$,

where:

- **Vvol UA-right** – volumetric blood flow in the right uterine artery (1 cm³ per cardiac cycle),
- **Vvol UA-left** – volumetric blood flow in the left uterine artery (1 cm³ per cardiac cycle),
- **Vuterus** – uterine volume (cm³).

The obtained results were analyzed using standard statistical methods.

Results

The mean age of patients in the study group was **27.33 ± 0.82 years**, while in the control group, it was **25.96 ± 0.99 years**.

Primiparous women constituted 11 (33.3%) in the main group and 14 (56%) in the control group. The parity in the main group was 2.12±1.04 deliveries, while in the control group, it was 1.6±1.78 deliveries.

In the medical history of the main group, surgical interventions during childbirth were reported in 6.1% of cases. Pregnancy termination (spontaneous miscarriages, pregnancy loss) occurred in 30.3% of the main group and 8% of the control group. In the assessment of fetal condition, fetal growth restriction syndrome was identified in 6.1% of cases, and antenatal fetal death was diagnosed in 24.2% of the main group, which was not observed in the control group.

The indications for cesarean section were as follows: premature detachment of a normally located placenta in 16.4% of cases, cephalopelvic disproportion in 9.1%, unsatisfactory labor progression and non-reassuring fetal condition in 9.1%, and placenta previa in 3.0% of cases. The gestational age at delivery was full-term in 60.6% of cases, preterm in 36.4%, and post-term in 6.1%.

The estimated blood loss in the main group averaged 1387.88 ± 60.26 ml, which was 29.5% higher than in the control group (406.8 ± 4.42 ml, $p < 0.001$). Among the 33 patients in the main group, blood loss up to 1000 ml was diagnosed in 4 (12.1%), severe blood loss (1000–1499 ml) in 14 (42.4%), and massive blood loss (1500–2100 ml) in 15 (45.5%) cases.

The study of Doppler parameters began with the measurement of uterine artery diameters, which was conducted on days 3–5 of the menstrual cycle. In the main group, the average diameter of the right uterine artery (UA) was 2.07 ± 0.02 mm, and the left UA was 2.01 ± 0.02 mm. These diameters were significantly smaller than in the control group, where the right UA diameter was 2.35 ± 0.02 mm and the left UA was 2.41 ± 0.02 mm ($p < 0.001$).

In the next stage, spectral Doppler ultrasonography was performed to measure the maximum, minimum, and mean blood flow velocities (Vmax; Vmin; Vmean) in each UA. A statistically significant reduction in peak systolic velocity (Vmax) in the uterine arteries was observed in the main group compared to the control group. The mean blood flow velocity (Vmax) in the main group was 28.37 ± 0.04 cm/s in the right UA versus 36.35 ± 0.33 cm/s in the control group, and 29.10 ± 0.03 cm/s in the left UA versus 37.65 ± 0.35 cm/s in the control group ($p < 0.001$).

A trend toward a decrease in end-diastolic velocity in the uterine arteries was noted. The mean minimum blood flow velocity (Vmin) in the right UA was 3.49 ± 0.04 cm/s in the main group versus 4.06 ± 0.07 cm/s in the control group, and in the left UA, it was 3.72 ± 0.03 cm/s versus 4.79 ± 0.08 cm/s ($p < 0.05$). In seven cases (21.2%) in the right UA and five cases (15.2%) in the left UA, zero end-diastolic blood flow velocity was observed.

The analysis of mean blood flow velocity (Vmean) in the main group showed that the average values were reduced to 5.42 ± 0.04 cm/s in the right UA and 4.99 ± 0.02 cm/s in the left UA, compared to the control group values of 6.59 ± 0.08 cm/s and 6.46 ± 0.08 cm/s, respectively.

The study included an analysis of angle-independent peripheral resistance indices (PI, RI, S/D) in the uterine arteries of patients after ligation of three pairs of uterine vessels and the application of compression sutures on the uterus. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Peripheral Resistance Indicators in the Studied Groups

Studied Parameters	E			
	C		M	
	MA right	MA left	MA right	MA left
Pulsation Index (PI)				
Resistance Index (RI)				
Systolic-Diastolic Ratio (SDR)				

Note: * - significant difference in the main group compared to the control group ($p < 0.001$). In the group with compression sutures and ligation of three pairs of uterine vessels against the background of pathological blood loss, high-resistance blood flow was observed, as evidenced by the mean values of peripheral vascular resistance indicators in the main group.

The mean values of the pulsatility index (PI) in the study group were significantly higher than in the control group, amounting to 3.83 ± 0.03 in the right uterine artery (UA) and 3.92 ± 0.03 in the left UA, compared to 2.32 ± 0.04 and 2.29 ± 0.04 in the control group ($p < 0.001$).

The resistance index (RI) was also significantly higher in the main group, reaching 0.97 ± 0.02 in the right UA and 0.99 ± 0.02 in the left UA, compared to 0.68 ± 0.01 and 0.63 ± 0.01 in the control group ($p < 0.001$).

The systolic-diastolic ratio (SDR) in the study group showed a tendency toward an increase, with values of 13.97 ± 0.03 in the right UA and 13.43 ± 0.04 in the left UA, compared to 9.52 ± 0.12 and 9.97 ± 0.11 in the control group.

We calculated the volumetric blood flow in the uterine arteries (1 cm³ per cardiac cycle) using a standard formula, with the results presented in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Volumetric Blood Flow in the Uterine Arteries

Studied Parameters	E			
	C		M	
	MA right	MA left	MA right	MA left
Volume Blood Flow, 1 cm³ per Cardiac Cycle (0.8 s)				

Note: * - significant difference in the main group compared to the control group ($p < 0.001$).

The average volumetric blood flow in the right uterine artery (UA) was 19.09 ± 0.03 , and in the left UA, it was 20.14 ± 0.03 , compared to 26.77 ± 0.19 and 25.88 ± 0.18 in the control group ($p < 0.001$). Notably, the volumetric blood flow in each UA was significantly lower than the control values—by 28.7% in the right UA and 22.2% in the left UA.

The uterine arterial perfusion index (UAPI) was calculated for this group of patients to determine uterine blood supply per 1 cm³ of the uterus through both uterine arteries per second. The calculations showed that the UAPI in the main group was significantly lower, indicating uterine hypoperfusion ($p < 0.001$). The UAPI in the main group was $0.86 \pm 0.01 \text{ s}^{-1}$, compared to $1.29 \pm 0.02 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the control group, which is 1.5 times lower than the control.

Considering that the round ligament and ovarian artery were ligated, we analyzed ovarian blood flow by assessing angle-independent intraovarian blood flow indices (PI, RI) in each ovary. The analysis showed a tendency for an increased resistance index in the main group, averaging 0.81 ± 0.02 in the right ovary and 0.90 ± 0.02 in the left ovary, compared to 0.54 ± 0.02 and 0.61 ± 0.02 in the control group, respectively ($p < 0.05$).

Additionally, an increase in the pulsatility index was observed, reaching 3.12 ± 0.01 and 3.07 ± 0.02 in the right and left ovaries, respectively, compared to 1.24 ± 0.03 and 1.58 ± 0.04 in the control group ($p < 0.05$).

Discussion

The analysis of uterine and ovarian blood supply in patients with pathological blood loss and organ-preserving surgeries during childbirth revealed a decrease in organ perfusion. The study showed that blood flow velocity (V_{max}) in the uterine arteries decreased 1.3 times, while the mean diameter of the uterine arteries was reduced by 11.9% in the right uterine artery (UA) and 16.6% in the left UA.

The reduction in uterine perfusion was confirmed not only by decreased blood flow in the uterine arteries but also by increased peripheral resistance. High-resistance blood flow was observed based on elevated resistance indices (RI) and pulsatility indices (PI). Measurements indicated an increase in PI by 39.4% in the right UA and 41.6% in the left UA, while RI increased by 29.9% in the right UA and 36.4% in the left UA.

When calculating blood flow per 1 cm³ per cardiac cycle in each uterine artery, a reduction in uterine perfusion was noted, likely due not only to pathological blood loss but also to organ-preserving surgeries. The volumetric blood flow in the main group decreased by 28.7% in the right UA and 22.2% in the left UA, leading to a 33.3% reduction in the uterine arterial perfusion index (UAPI) compared to the control group. A decline in volumetric blood flow in the uterine arteries results in a decrease in the UAPI, indicating uterine hypovascularization.

The study of intraovarian circulation revealed a decline in Doppler parameters, as evidenced by increased peripheral resistance indices. In the group undergoing combined organ-preserving surgeries, PI increased by 39.7% in the right ovary and 51.5% in the left ovary, while RI rose by 33.3% in the right ovary and 32.2% in the left ovary.

Conclusion

For the proper functioning of the uterus and ovaries, a well-maintained vascular network is essential. The condition of the vascular bed directly affects the maintenance and growth of developing follicles in the ovary, as well as their potential transformation into the corpus luteum and its function [1]. Insufficient angiogenesis is also associated with the absence of cyclic changes in intraovarian blood flow, characterized by high resistance index (RI) values and low maximum blood flow velocity [2].

When ovarian blood supply is compromised, the function of the corpus luteum—the primary source of endogenous progesterone—declines. As a result, corpus luteum insufficiency (hypoluteinism) may develop, which, in cases of fertilization, can lead to early pregnancy loss.

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